

Assessing FAIRness of Record-based Repositories for Enhanced Interoperability

Authors: John Graybeal,* Nancy J. Hoebelheinrich, Julianne Christopher, Erik Schultes, Christopher Erdmann, Barbara Magagna, Ismael Kherroubi Garcia, Darya Pokutnaya, Lisa M. Mayer, Christine R. Kirkpatrick

*Corresponding author contact: jbgraybeal@sdsc.edu

How to cite this paper:

Graybeal, J. *et al.* (2025) Assessing FAIRness of Record-based Repositories for Enhanced Interoperability, *GO FAIR US*, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13993533

Published: May 16th, 2025

Copyright © 2025 by author(s) and GO FAIR US.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License ([CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)).

Abstract

FAIR Principles are defined without regard to the structure of data they discuss, and many analyses have interpreted that structure in the most abstract way possible. However, in most practical interpretations and applications of the FAIR Principles, users assume the primary organization of data is a dataset (itself defined as either a single static file, or a static collection of files, containing the data). Thus, file-based repositories are well-served by the current prescribed and measured approaches for making data FAIR. However, the FAIR Principles are not so straightforwardly applicable to “record-based” repositories; those that are not file-based. In this paper, we outline considerations for evaluating the extent to which record-based repositories adhere to the FAIR Principles (their ‘FAIRness’), and propose approaches and sufficient technical guidance to allow others to evaluate FAIRness of this type of repository. The approaches we introduce also apply to a variety of file-based repositories, including files that change over time, are data calculations rather than data collections, or reflect complex models within the file.

Keywords

Open science, FAIR Principles, FAIR Assessment, Record-based Repositories

1. Definitions

For clarity, we adopt these definitions to support our discussion of interoperability for record-based repositories.

Report: an output from a data repository that presents information in response to a particular query (typically in this document, about the Entities and Entity Types as discussed below).

File-based repository: a repository that principally organizes and presents its scientific data in the form of data files (or collections of data files). Metadata primarily describe those data files as a whole, and may not

account for changes if the file is dynamic (growing or being modified). Users who want a narrower collection of data typically must frame that request relative to an entire data file or collection, and any summary metadata that may describe it.

Record-based repository: a repository that principally manages its scientific data in the form of individual (atomic) data records that are dynamically aggregated into a collection or report, generally in response to (or anticipating) specific requests from users. (In some cases, the ‘data record’ may consist of all collected information about a particular entity instance, defined below.) The dynamic aggregation means that the data records change over time, and so versioning the data may be necessary. Metadata for the presented data may describe the collection or report as a whole but not describe in detail what data are contained in the collection or report. Alternatively, the metadata may describe in detail all the information contained within the report. Other types of record-based data or repositories include ‘stream-based’ and ‘time series’ data, as these share the fundamental characteristics of aggregating individual records into a larger report. NoSQL databases, graph databases, and triple stores also have the characteristics of record-based repositories, in which the ‘individual records’ and their aggregated form (collection or report) are defined according to the particular repository and data model(s) it implements.

Mixed-structure repository: a repository that combines file-based representations and record-based representations of the data in its presentations of data.

Dataset: a collection of scientific values about a named Entity (see definition below) that can be discovered, accessed, analyzed, and documented as an unchanging block of data. A data block in a dataset may be a single file, or a set of related files (also called a data collection). In the more general sense, a dataset can also be considered a set of (one or more) records that compose an unchanging block of data, subject to the same functions described in the first sentence. In some situations, data files, data collections, and data record collections may be dynamic, but by versioning data files, data collections, and sets of records we can transform a changing block or collection of data into the ‘unchanging block of data’ that we define as a Dataset in this document. (Note that the unchanging Dataset as defined might have a version.)

Entity type: a name assigned to a group of entity instances that share common characteristics. In the science domain, entity types are typically taxonomic, class, or category names that serve to represent a population of entity instances (for example, patient or assay). In our context, we want entity types and entity instances to have globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifiers (GUPRIs).

Entity or entity instance: also known as a data entity, data object, digital object, or (in GO FAIR) object, this is (a digital representation of) an instance of a particular entity type; for example, an entity type may be ‘tissue sample’, and a corresponding entity will be (a digital description of) a particular tissue sample with a given identifier. Note that generally speaking, this identifier may or may not be FAIR, and may or may not be globally unique, persistent, and resolvable (see Identifier definition below), but we would like those conditions to be met. For in a FAIR system, it is generally the case that if an Entity is of significance, we want to represent it as a ‘first class object’ on the internet, with all the necessary metadata that entails.

Identifier: a string of text characters that refers to a particular digital, conceptual, or real-world entity. This document emphasizes the use of particular types of identifiers with particular characteristics, using the following acronyms:

GUPRI: a Globally Unique Persistent Resolvable Identifier is a fundamental component in the FAIR Principles. A GUPRI refers to a unique entity, lasts for a long time (ideally forever), and when put into a web browser or queried by software tools, it should resolve to meaningful content about the thing being identified. This requires a GUPRI to begin ‘http://’ or ‘https://’.

IRI: an Internationalized Resource Identifier is an internet protocol standard which improves upon previous web identifier protocols (notably, the URL in your browser) to support international characters (like characters with accent marks). IRIs can serve as GUPRIs when used as part of an appropriately designed system, and their use in this document reflects their alignment with, and existing use in, the repositories being addressed.

Static entity: an entity that is considered fixed from the moment it is first received by a repository and presented to users. By definition, the static entity's content cannot be modified via deletion, change or addition; any such changes, if possible at all, result in the creation of a new static entity (which may be considered a version of a previous entity).

Dynamic entity: an entity that may change over time through deletions, changes, or additions to the content. In the least FAIR scenario, these changes are neither tracked nor versioned, so there is no way to know what information may have made up the entity at any previous time. In the most FAIR scenario, all changes are tracked and any version of the entity may be recovered with the appropriate identifier (see Dataset).

2. Problem Statement

Most record-based repositories provide limited or no metadata about any aggregation of data that is delivered to users, and provide limited metadata about each data variable in the aggregation. Since the aggregations themselves are often generated dynamically, the lack of (for example) a unique identifier that would re-generate the same aggregation, or point to the documentation that describes it, is a significant obstacle to understanding and reusing the data set or reusing results obtained with it.

FAIR Principles are defined without regard to the structure of the data they address, and many analyses (e.g., *Interpreting FAIR*, n.d.) have presented that structure in the most abstract way possible. That said, in most practical interpretations and applications of the FAIR Principles, users assume the primary organization of data is a static dataset, which they consider in those cases to be either a single file, or a collection of files, containing the data. This makes for an attractively feasible level of documentation, since providing detailed metadata for a file or collection of files seems within reach to many data providers. Nominally, file-based repositories are thus well-served by the current descriptive and measurement approaches for making data FAIR.

On the other hand, explanations like those in GO FAIR's definition of FAIR Principle *F1* (n.d.) describe 'data' as being of any size or organization, even to the level of an individual concept or data value. This detailed possibility reflects an automation-oriented goal for FAIR data, where computers are integral to creating the data, documenting that data, and then later discovering, accessing, and reusing the data. It also more closely matches the data structure used by record-based repositories, which may deal with data at a much more atomic level than do file-based repositories. We therefore consider what FAIRness looks like in record-based repositories.

How can we apply to a record-based repository the questions and processes that are used to evaluate the FAIRness of a dataset or repository? More fundamentally, how can such a repository be made FAIR? We must agree on a set of approaches that will maximize the ability of such repositories to interoperate with each other, and produce FAIR results for computers and humans using their data. To succeed in the short term, we must show that the advantages provided by the new approaches outweigh their implementation costs. ("We can't rebuild all the repositories.")

We believe the approaches described herein offer a technical foundation for the FAIR assessment of record-based repositories. What's more, these approaches are sufficiently general to be applied to file-based repositories, simply by considering a 'data file' as another type of data entity, and being prepared to describe its content and define how it is versioned.

3. Determining a Repository's Entity Types

If the repository is to make its entities FAIR, the first question is: what are the repository's entity types? Defining this in advance for a large number of repositories is not possible for a small organization, as a data architect must individually assess each repository. However, repository managers are well placed to propose answers to that question. Their answers will be credible because the answers reflect the goals for the repository, and ensure the FAIR evaluation process will target those goals and produce the most useful and accurate results. The evaluation process will also independently identify—through a FAIR lens—mismatches between the proposed entity types and the entity types that are actually implemented.

The taxonomy of entity type categories that follows is designed to do 3 things: (1) help a repository's managers recognize and describe entity types that their repository delivers to its customers; (2) envision what these entity types need to look like if they are FAIR; and (3) assess how much effort the entity type merits to make it more FAIR. Consultation with a FAIR-aware data architect may be helpful in dealing with these technical activities.

3.1. Observations Applicable to All Entity Type Categories

An important consideration when assessing whether a repository manages an entity type is whether the repository acts as an authority for the entity. Does the repository create descriptive information about entities of that type, or is it simply reusing characteristics or labels that have been fully described in other sources? For example, if tissue samples are fully identified, named, and described primarily in the repository, the repository can be considered responsible for those entities and their FAIRness. But if the tissue sample is registered and managed in a separate samples repository, we can assume the entity's primary FAIRness is the responsibility of the other repository, though entity users must preserve and present the entity's identifier.

Regarding semantic entity types (ontologies including controlled vocabularies, and concepts including terms), a similar principle applies: for any concept in an ontology, the author of that ontology is responsible for maintaining the concept's descriptive metadata to ensure FAIRness. Repositories often use terminological categories and organizing principles that are well known and defined in community practice and literature. Typically, these terminologies closely mimic terminologies that are already defined in external semantic resources. However, if the application does not explicitly associate the concepts it presents (via a user interface or API) with an ontology, both human and machine users cannot be sure what the concepts mean. Explicitly associating a repository's concepts with identical or closely matched concepts in external ontologies is an important step toward creating a FAIR system.

3.2. Core Entity Types

We define a 'core entity type' for a repository as a primary entity type of fundamental interest for the purposes of the repository, as declared by the repository owners and managers and confirmed during a FAIR evaluation process. Consider a database of tissue samples from clinical trials. This specific description contains the database's core entity type: tissue samples from clinical trials. We will use such an entity type as an example in subsequent sections.

The FAIR assessment process should determine, with as much precision as possible, what concept(s) describe each core entity type that the repository presents. Any attempt to assess the repository's FAIRness, or offer recommendations to improve its FAIRness, must first elucidate this list of core entity types for the repository. Ideally, the entity types are named and described using terms from community-managed controlled vocabularies.

3.3. Secondary Entity Types

Many repositories go beyond representing a simple set of core entity types. To address the widest possible range of repositories, we must consider more advanced scenarios, including additional entities of interest to the repository (Incidental Entity Types), how users are able to select desired subsets of individual entities (Selectable Entity Types; Entity Views; and most flexibly, General Queries), and data collection that takes place over time (Data Streams).

3.3.1. Incidental Entity Types

A repository may collect information about entity types beyond its core entities. For example, a repository about tissue samples may also register detailed data about sample procedures. The repository may even present a ‘sample procedures’ view that lets users find all samples obtained from particular procedures or other related characteristics. In this case, the repository is also managing a ‘sample procedures’ entity type, even if it is only used as a means to filter views in a user interface.

Incidental entity types are crucial for capturing the scientific provenance of the core entities. They are also often valuable to scientists interested in similar topics. Therefore, it is appropriate to encourage adoption of FAIR Principles for handling the corresponding entity data. However, depending upon the repository’s resources, these incidental entity types may need to receive less emphasis than core entity types.

3.3.2. Selectable Entity Types

A repository may let the user search for tissue samples according to particular criteria (filters or other constraints) as described above, or may provide views that have been pre-selected according to particular criteria. This is a qualified case of entity type: the filter or constraint criteria enforce a narrower selection of entities, the description of which requires specific information. (For example, instead of “all patients”, the description of a narrower selection might be “all male patients over 40 with kidney disease”.) The key consideration in deciding whether these selections need more detailed metadata is whether the user (person or machine) viewing the result needs contextual knowledge about the resulting selection.

To consider it another way, any repository’s query response that is presented as a selection or a report—either in UI, API, or file format—needs its own FAIR treatment and FAIR metadata. In this respect, a chosen selection or report from the repository needs to be described as an entity, with the metadata necessary to make it findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. (See “Manage Versioned Entity Reports” below.) Ideally, the selection or report will get an identifier that allows regeneration, and metadata that makes it understandable (to people and machines) in its delivered form. In particular, outputs that are presented in stand-alone form (as files, or as a resource via API to another computer) should have embedded metadata that fully describes the output, including how it was generated (what conditions, query, filters, constraints, and versioning allows the result to be replicated).

3.3.3. Entity Views

A repository of tissue samples may not have a single database or data model for all its tissue samples, and it may present only certain information depending on what is searched for or requested. For example, our hypothetical tissue sample repository may have one view that is strictly for tissues from any organism used in sample assays, and another view that is strictly for human tissue samples.

For FAIR purposes, these customized views are equivalent to the selectable entity types described above. The entity views need to be described as an entity type would be, and they need to include the necessary metadata

for their data to be understood and reusable. An important way to consider these customized views is that the repository is providing a “standard report” about its contents, and the subject of the standard report can be considered an entity type, albeit possibly a very specific entity type.

3.3.4. General Queries

A queryable database allows an arbitrarily large number of queries, which result in a similarly large number of possible entity types. This situation presents a complex and subtle scenario for defining entity types. In this case, we can discover and evaluate the appropriate entity types for FAIR evaluation by finding the appropriate level of abstraction to define them.

At its most flexible, a queryable database has a large number of entities directly represented, and the number of selectable entity types for reporting is arbitrarily big (think of complex WHERE queries in SQL or SPARQL). In this case, the only possible response is to provide appropriate metadata about the corpus of the database, the specific query requested, and the timestamp of the response. In such cases, the FAIR evaluation criteria must be applicable to any possible query.

If the database is targeting a specific set of entity types, appropriate metadata about those entities should be defined sufficiently (by the repository and/or the community) so that queries about those entity types may be evaluated for FAIRness more specifically. For example, if the database only contains information about tissue samples, sampling events, and sample procedures, only a few query types may be important for each entity type, and the entity-query combinations present a manageable number of queries that define the entities to make FAIR. This kind of customized metadata generation—specific to query-entity-combinations—is beyond the scope of this document, but suggests a direction to follow.

3.3.5. Data Streams (aka Dynamic Data, Time Series Data, or Longitudinal Data)

Many data collection efforts involve a series of updating data values that follow particular formats, with the data being collected or ‘logged’ in data files or other structures. The data formats may be prescriptive about the metadata and data content of each data record, or, at the other extreme, say only how a record is terminated and another record begun. (In the most literal interpretation, every data collection that has more than one version—even a Microsoft Word document—can be viewed as a data stream. Such an understanding can help create rigorous data management models.)

Data streams may be defined as being from a particular data source—for example, a specific instrument with a given serial number—or from a series of sources that occupy the same role (the oxygen sensor at a specific depth on a specific ocean buoy, or the most accurate blood pressure sensor associated with a given patient at any given time). Software can compose data streams into new data streams, in which case the composing software is the direct source. However, metadata should also point to originating sources, not just the most recent source. For maximum interoperability, the complete provenance of the data collection and computation processes—if possible, including provenance of the data collection instruments—should be available for any data value.

As with the flexible entities above—particularly queryable databases—the appropriate level for generating metadata and evaluating FAIRness is at the data stream level, but the amount of detail that should be provided about that data stream depends on the data stream’s source and purpose. While data streams that have rigidly controlled content should have metadata that describes that content, data streams that consist of “all transmissions from source X” should have metadata to describe source X in detail.

As described elsewhere, the core identifier for the data stream conceptually incorporates its past, present, and future data. To describe a static subset of that data stream requires creating an identifier that allows the

referenced static subset of data to be retrieved and contextualized. (The same requirement applies to describe a static subset of a dynamic data set or data set collection.) The system that provides the data stream to the user is responsible for generating these identifiers and the corresponding static subset of data, whether the system does so by rule (e.g., putting begin and end timestamps in an identifier) or by execution (e.g., “every day, I create another data copy and an identifier for it,” or “I create an identifier for every request and archive a copy of that data.”)

4. Pursuing FAIR Principles in Record-based Repositories

In this section, we address software engineering approaches that support greater FAIRness in records-based repositories. We assume any repository will contain local identifiers, and will generate some dynamic pages or reports for entities it manages. With this as a starting point, we consider how such repositories could meet the goals of the FAIR Principles.

The strategies outlined below are interconnected, with the most foundational strategies presented first. The more foundational strategies are also simpler in concept and execution. It is not required to implement all the strategies, but the foundational strategies make the later strategies feasible. Each additional strategy supports another level of FAIR services, at some additional cost. A single system (re)design that implements all the desired strategies at once is more efficient than implementing strategies at different times.

When IRI strategies like these are adopted by a repository, an important step toward FAIRness is to make the repository’s practices explicit and declare they will not change. Individual users will naturally take advantage of patterns used in identifiers, but system developers can only take advantage of those patterns if it is clear they will remain stable—otherwise systems that leverage them will break when they change. Thus claiming credit for FAIR policies is itself a positive FAIR approach: it reassures users, encourages reuse of the FAIR data, and encourages other repositories to adopt similar patterns and practices.

In this section, we use examples drawn from the Immune Epitope Database (IEDB). The IEDB has many characteristics common to record-based observatories, and also shows considerable linked data adoption, a trait that is common in FAIR systems. While this analysis uses only information visible from the IEDB interfaces in 2024, in fact IEDB has in many cases explicitly designed their system and its identifiers consistently with FAIR Principles, as described in their Core Trust Seal application (Blazeska, 2023). As it explains: “In essence, the IEDB is a database of epitopes and the assays in which they were tested, and all relevant details about each assay are included.”

Figures 1a and 1b.

(A) Expose GUPRI Identifiers for Entity Types

To make record-based repositories FAIR, one foundational strategy is to use GUPRIs for all referenced entities (either by replacing existing local identifiers internally, or mapping them to external identifiers on data export). Note that, in strategy (A), we are designing the identifier to be resolvable, but the resolution process and product might be very basic. In the next strategy we discuss richer landing pages for identifiers.

In the IEDB repository (see figures 1a and 1b at left):

- Entity types are in facets on the left and column headers in the reports: Epitope, Epitope Source, Receptor, Assay, MHC Restriction, Host, Disease, Reference, Antigen. If you select T-cell, B-cell, or MHC filters in the UI you can see additional facets (entity types).
 - Other entity types could satisfy data provenance attributes in the metadata; for example, people, organizations, or projects.
 - In some cases, the entities appear as fields in data views (a Reference Author, for example), but these also can be treated as entities in their own right.
 - Local identifiers for entity individuals might be text strings ('homo sapiens', 'John Smith'), numeric identifiers ('24786'), or full GUPRIs in the form of IRIs. Any of these choices might represent an individual, or a class of individuals, or an external object; for our purposes we do not need to distinguish between those cases.
- In any of these cases, a system can expose the identifiers representing entity individuals as GUPRI identifiers, and often IEDB chooses this approach.

(B) Resolve Identifiers to Entity Reports

- A second strategy is the resolution of entity-based identifiers into a view or report for the individual entity. In IEDB we see (Figure 2):
- An epitope has local ID 24786.
- The IRI for this epitope is <https://iedb.org/epitope/24786>, which is declared the GUPRI for that epitope (therefore, the IRI will always represent the same epitope and resolve to information about it).
- The report that you see (in Figure 2) when that IRI is ds to that unique entity ID and IRI.

- The IEDB system consistently references that epitope using its full (IRI) identifier—either explicitly or as an active link—to enable immediate entity resolution for people and machines.

These approaches make the repository’s data more FAIR, and by following best practices for Linked Open Data, also make the website more usable for all its viewers.

The screenshot shows the IEDB (Immune Epitope Database & Tools) search results page. The current filters include 'Include Positive Assays'. The search results are displayed in a table with columns for IEDB ID, Epitope, Antigen, Organism, # References, and # Assays. The table shows 1630551 records found, with the current page displaying 25 records per page. The highlighted row is for IEDB ID 24786, which corresponds to the epitope HSLGKWLGHDPDKF, associated with the antigen Myelin proteolipid protein (UniProt:P60202) and the organism Mus musculus (mouse). The table also shows other related entries such as 44920 (NLVPMVATV) for Human herpesvirus 5 and 123885 (cardiolipin) for Gallus gallus (chicken).

Figure 2. The IEDB display for an entity instance, in this case epitope 24786. The user interface displays data for that entity when resolving its IRI (<https://iedb.org/epitope/24786>).

(C) Manage Versioned Entity Reports

A feature of many repositories and web services is that the displayed content at an IRI—the ‘entity report’ page described above—may change over time. Just like in many file-based datasets, new data may be appended, or existing data may be corrected. Thus, the repository must implement a strategy for representing the state of information about an entity at a given period of time. If the system was not designed from the start to support such a strategy, adding versioning later may be complicated, depending on the approach taken. Any such strategy must, in some way, track all the entity’s changes between each version.

- Typically, the fundamental piece of information saying what the core entity is—in our example, the IRI <https://iedb.org/epitope/24786>—serves that purpose.
- In addition, a versioned report requires information in the IRI that uniquely identifies the version of data being displayed. A variety of effective practices exist for versioned IRIs.
 - The ‘version-info’ is often appended as either additional items in the path (for example <https://exampleiedb.org/epitope/24786/{version-info}>), or as a query string (for example

<https://example.org/epitope/24786?version={version-info}>

- The version-info may be a meaningless or named string identifier, or a date-timestamp when the version was generated (e.g., *ISO 8601*).
- If the resulting ‘versioned IRI’ is a GUPRI, we can say the versioned entity has been published (if only on that website).

(D) Issue Custom Report Identifiers

A customized report (for example, one based on a unique set of filters or constraints) also needs to have its own identifier.

- For example, users of IEDB can select arbitrary combinations of filters to generate new reports; these filter combinations can reasonably be expected to always produce the same type of report, though included data items will change over time as more data is added to the repository. Giving each filter combination its own identifier reference in user interfaces and APIs (including data downloads) supports data validation and reuse.
 - At the moment, the format of the corresponding IRI in IEDB’s User Interface relies on cookies (for example, the IRI https://iedb.org/result_v3.php?cookie_id=fe31e4). This only works for the machine making that request, and only while its browser retains the cookie information.
 - Meanwhile, the metadata of the resulting download data set describes the search parameters and the date of the search, which are important metadata values to have. However, no other attributes or identifiers are presented.
- For this use case, the pattern for the IRI could use sub-paths or query-based IRIs, but the chosen implementation cannot conflict with the pattern used for versions. (Those could be designed as an additional parameter of the filters.)
- For interoperability across related repositories, there should be a common way to describe entity type identifiers that can capture the same constraint information. As a simple example, an epitope report that includes unvalidated data could be expressed as https://example.org/epitope?include_unvalidated=true. (All the related repositories must agree on this syntax for including unvalidated data.)

Note that the more rigorous and consistent the use of identifiers in the repository, the more rigorous and consistent will be the identifiers for entity types used in custom report constraints.

(E) Agree on Shared Entity Type Identifiers

To make these strategies viable across a collection of repositories (for example, across all repositories in an organization), we want a common way to refer to each entity type and its entity instances across the environment, so that the same terms can be used to search any set of repositories in the environment.

- The collection of repositories should have a single way to refer to each entity type.
 - Example: Referencing the entity type ‘epitope’ by the same GUPRI identifier throughout the system is valuable.
 - Allowing that identifier to be annotated semantically by multiple preferred labels (one for each language) preserves understanding in a multilingual user base.
- Ideally, the entire collection of repositories agrees on a single ‘reference identifier system’ for each repository’s entity instances (see first strategy above). If every repository mints its own identifier for

epitope 24786 from IEDB, harmonization requires extremely demanding mapping. (Sometimes mapping is impossible given the number of instances and different principles for their identification.) Mapping across different identifier systems is a necessary backup when the community can not agree on a single identifier for an entity type or entity instance.

If the community agrees on common identifiers for common entity types (like ‘epitope’), this creates a common vocabulary for those ‘reference entity types.’ The common identifiers, when resolved, should yield clear definitions using well-defined community standards; for example, agreed semantic definitions in RDF (RDF Working Group, 2014) or JSON-LD (*JSON for Linked Data*, n.d.), or FAIR Digital Objects (Anders *et al.*, 2023; Magnana *et al.*, 2025). This approach is expanded in the following strategy.

The approaches in this strategy are based on extensive experience in the semantic domain (ontologies and vocabularies), where multiple authorities exist for semantic identifiers of all domains and hierarchy levels. While the initial goal is always to agree on shared existing identifiers, in some scenarios that won’t happen. In those cases, the use of common standards to define identifiers allows mapping technologies to provide necessary interoperability.

(F) Standardize Representations for Data and Metadata

This strategy describes how to make your metadata and data artifacts interoperable by following well-defined specifications that a computer can process and validate. We focus in this strategy on specifications for digital artifacts, not the specifications for the communication interfaces— those are addressed in the following two strategies.

For technical or social reasons, it may not be possible or appropriate to change your internal data and metadata representations to make them more easily understood by other individuals or machines. If you already have a community specification for metadata and data artifacts, but the specification does not support the identifiers we’ve discussed above, you can still become more FAIR without changing your existing specification. Instead, you can add support for new specifications that are more interoperable. By providing the more interoperable specifications, you will benefit future applications and users who may not have your local knowledge, and simplify working with your data and metadata using external tools, including advanced explanatory systems such as Large Language Models.

The ideal specification for describing and presenting digital artifacts has the following characteristics:

- It is clearly documented and maintained by a standards organization, or at least by a community that uses, recommends and maintains the specification.
- Its documentation and any supporting code or examples are openly available, and validation software exists.
- It is widely used across projects, tools, communities, domains, government entities, and countries.
- It supports composition of the contents (whether data or metadata). Most data artifact types—along with the metadata that describe them—support hierarchical components. The specification must therefore be able to represent the same hierarchies. Most data artifact types can be decomposed at least to the level of streams of individual values, so the specification for the corresponding metadata must be able to reference and document those streams.
- It recognizes and describes versioning in both metadata and data artifacts.
- It avoids embedding implicit information in its structure, aside from basic organization. For example, a specification that assigns each of the first 10 lines to specific content, or that requires parsing a complex

format (such as PDF or natural language text) in order to obtain the key attributes, will be difficult or impossible for machines (and sometimes people) to understand.

- It integrates standardized semantic concepts (defined using identifiers like the ones described above) wherever appropriate in the data or metadata.
- It specifies most or all of the necessary constructs for any person or tool to work with the data/metadata artifact and present its content to a third party.
- If a metadata specification, it allows the metadata values to be embedded with the data that they describe. (Alternatively, at a minimum, it allows the metadata to unambiguously reference the described data and where it can be obtained.)
- If a data specification, it allows a data artifact to point to its corresponding metadata.

There are few specifications that satisfy all of these criteria, but we summarize below a few examples that offer significant capabilities. All three of these examples are meta-specifications in that they constrain the fundamental content and structure of the metadata (or data), but do not define the entire profile for the published metadata or data to follow. It is up to a specific community —or a generalist community like Zenodo.org, Dataverse.org, or Google.com— to describe the detailed specification for their artifacts of interest. For example, the detailed DCAT catalog vocabulary (Albertoni *et al.*, 2024) for data sets and data services can be supported using a CEDAR Workbench (CEDAR, 2021) template specification, so that anyone filling out that form will be creating a DCAT-compatible metadata description.¹

Example 1: W3C Semantic Web Standards (RDF, SKOS, OWL, and more)

The semantic web specifications put forth by the W3C standards body were designed to define concepts and relationships that enabled logical inference across a collection of semantic web artifacts. The atomic unit of declaration in the semantic web is a triple, which consists of a subject, a property or relation, and an object (or data value), which together read like a simple sentence. Importantly, all these components (except the data value) are represented as identifiers, which can serve to link all the triples into a graph or web.

The basic framework of the semantic web is RDF (Resource Description Framework), upon which many other specifications are layered. The specification for SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) facilitates defining terms in thesauri and taxonomies), while OWL (Web Ontology Language) defines a rich modeling language that can be used to create complex knowledge models.

Example 2: CEDAR Workbench Metadata Template Specification

The Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval developed the CEDAR Workbench metadata system to make organizing and filling out metadata descriptions easier and more precise. The template specification provides an uber-standard which all templates must follow, and in turn each metadata template (that users create for their metadata needs) defines the format that metadata instances must follow. Users create metadata instances by filling out metadata forms in a simple user interface, or systems can generate metadata instances automatically. The specifications are in JSON-LD, with the metadata instances convertible to JSON or RDF.

CEDAR was designed for compatibility with existing Semantic Web identifiers, and the CEDAR implementation

¹ Many communities now specify detailed metadata standards for their data sets and implement them throughout their data processing and submission pipelines. See for example the Adaptive Immune Receptor Repertoire work (AIRR Standards Working Group, n.d.) and the neuroscience community's Brain Imaging Data Structure metadata description (BIDS Contributors, n.d.).

deployed at the Stanford Center for Biomedical Informatics Research uses semantic resources from the BioPortal ontology repository (Whetzel *et al.*, 2011). (BioPortal resources can be submitted by anyone and are not limited to any particular research domain; they include many biomedical ontologies.) BioPortal contains a copy of almost all mature OBO Foundry ontologies (OBO Technical Working Group, n.d.) and imports the most significant biomedical vocabularies from the Unified Medical Language System (Bodenreider, 2004), so CEDAR can also use those semantic resources.

CEDAR specifications can be used outside of the core system, as some general-purpose repositories are already doing (Olson & Corker, 2024; Lippincott, 2024). Standalone software has been written to convert CEDAR metadata instances into nanopublications (Kuhn, 2019).

Example 3: FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs)

FAIR Digital Objects, with their implementing technology nanopublications, are the most basic collection of information that contains a statement along with metadata describing the statement. These primitives can be constructed (translated) from metadata collections of other forms (RDF triples, JSON-LD attributes, CEDAR metadata fields, schema.org variables...), and could serve as a lingua franca for establishing a common collection of interoperable metadata (or data) from multiple repositories.

As with CEDAR, nanopublications provide the framing infrastructure in which metadata declarations can be made, and support RDF as an underlying model, while requiring an explicit profile to specify the metadata required by any given community.

(G) Provide Common Services

Once identifiers and standard artifact representations are available, services can be developed that make use of those FAIR data products. These can be delivered at three levels, as (i) internal services that provide FAIR data to other parts of the system, (ii) publicly visible services that make your data and metadata directly accessible and reusable, or (iii) standalone services that build on the first two capabilities.

At the first level, you may already be indexing many of your key products so that they can be searched by your own system. Adding the previously created identifiers and standardized products to your indexing systems will allow many more powerful and FAIR products to be developed. This forms the foundation of a FAIR architecture that can support many enhancements over a long period of time.

At the next level you can create publicly available data and metadata access and publishing services for your FAIR data and metadata. (The next strategy considers how to make these public interfaces as interoperable as possible.) As this makes your standardized FAIR data products available to the widest possible audience, it multiplies the power of your FAIR improvements, and your repository as a whole. Existing users of your system, who can relatively easily adapt their software to find and obtain all of the products that your repository publishes, while being confident that your identifiers won't suddenly change and your terminologies and metadata attributes will continue to be understandable and accessible.

Furthermore, the benefit of delivering FAIR data products goes far beyond your existing users. By taking into account the expectations of your community and external system providers, your visibility and impact can grow significantly. Making your data files visible and understandable to Google Search, Google Dataset Search (n.d.), and all the other search engines that use the same specifications,² creates an extremely FAIR system. Such a

² A principal specification used by Google Search is the schema.org standard (<https://schema.org>), which has now been augmented by the extension Bioschemas (<https://bioschemas.org>). Preparing your data to be compatible with Google

system supports not just search capabilities, but other tools that can add value and visibility to your system. Some of these tools can easily convert standardized products into other formats, for example from well-specified JSON-LD or RDF to nanopublications (Kuhn *et al.*, 2018), and build more sophisticated indexing and analysis capabilities on top of those results.

(H) Offer Common Access Methods

Repositories should offer common access methods for providing their metadata/data based on the IRIs that reference those data/metadata. These methods should be accommodating both to human users and to pre-programmed machine interfaces in order to be fully FAIR.

- If the community accepts common identifiers for common entity types (like epitopes) in their APIs, this constitutes a common vocabulary.
- If any repository that resolves its own created identifiers presents commonly structured views (to human users) and computer-parseable artifacts (to computer applications), this makes it possible for people and computers to explore the content in very FAIR and extensible ways.
- If the community's varied patterns for constructing IRI-based requests can be specified in a generic way, then it may be possible to request common information across the ecosystem. In other words, it is acceptable for one repository's API pattern to differ from another, so long as each pattern can be explicitly defined (such as <https://example.org/epitope/1234>) and software visiting both repositories can make a similar query across them by accounting for the pattern difference (such as <https://example2.org/epitopes?action=retrieve&identifier=1234&format=jsonld>).
- If a common set of expected metadata parameters is defined as part of each entity report, then the computer can correctly account for key aspects of the entity data. An example of scientific metadata parameters is to include for each patient observation their height, weight, and blood pressure. An example of administrative metadata parameters is to include the time, source, and curation applied for every data record. For example, FHIR specifications define the format of specific record types, the metadata that should be included with them, and the vocabularies to use in their parameters (though some of the specifications are not fully released and adopted).
- If a common format can be agreed on for delivering the results, then you have significant interoperability. Examples of such formats include comma-separated value (CSV) responses with explicitly specified metadata formats, or JSON-LD responses that organize the core entity information using the same attribute names. Defining your content format using a shared computable model provides the maximum level of format interoperability.

As is evident in these examples, community agreement is typically required in order to establish access methods that become widely adopted standards. This is feasible when the community has shared interests and/or shared direction, even for very advanced interoperability requirements. For example, a community like the Adaptive Immune Receptor Repertoire (AIRR) sequencing community requires highly specific metadata in order to make the sequencing operations reproducible. The AIRR standards working group works to declare these standards in a computable format that can be applied and validated with automated tools. In this way, the community achieved a high level of interoperability among the community members who contribute AIRR sequence data, and the repositories that house that data. This standardization enabled all users of the data to benefit from the increased

Dataset Search is described in Google developer materials at <https://developers.google.com/search/docs/appearance/structured-data/dataset>.

interoperability, even if they are not AIRR community members themselves.

How do we evaluate the FAIRness of repositories and their record-based entities?

In A persona-specific method to assess the FAIRness of data repositories (Hoebelheinrich *et al.*, 2025), we described an evaluation approach that includes technical assessment as well as collecting and assessing human responses from the repositories. In the case of record-based repositories, there are few if any existing approaches to perform a FAIR technical assessment, since traditional file-based evaluation approaches assume a different data model.

Our proposed FAIRness evaluation for record-based repositories parallels our persona-based evaluation approach for file-based repositories. To that, our approach adds a process to define the basic entities being managed by the repository, and establishes guidance for expected practices to create and resolve identifiers for those basic entities. These expected practices parallel those used for file-based repositories to identify and resolve data files, and can be applied to the content of file-based repositories to create and resolve more granular identifiers within data files.

As with file-based repositories, the actual technical evaluation of the record-based repositories considers how many of the recommended FAIR practices have been instantiated for the core entities in the repository. More sophisticated practices around those entities, including generating FAIR identifiers (GUPRIs) for entity instances and serving authoritative data and metadata records about them, indicate increasing FAIR maturity levels. The results of that evaluation are combined with the other persona-based evaluations to form a complete picture of the repository's FAIR maturity.

We believe these guidelines provide a useful strategy to inform the evaluations of a record-based repository's FAIR efforts, and offer the repository useful technical approaches to increase the FAIRness of its data and metadata, and thereby its interoperability with the wider research community.

References

- AIRR Standards Working Group (no date) Standards Working Group, The Antibody Society. Available at: <https://www.antibodysociety.org/the-airr-community/airr-working-groups/standards-working-group/> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- Albertoni, R. *et al.* (2024) 'Data Catalog Vocabulary – Version 3'. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2024/REC-vocab-dcat-3-20240822/>.
- BIDS Contributors (no date) 'Common data types and metadata - Brain Imaging Data Structure 1.10.0'. Available at: <https://bids-specification.readthedocs.io/en/stable/derivatives/common-data-types.html> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- Blazeska, N. (2023) 'IEDB CoreTrustSeal Approved Application', IEDB Solutions, 10 October. Available at: <https://help.iedb.org/hc/en-us/articles/19458668574491-IEDB-CoreTrustSeal-Approved-Application> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- Bodenreider, O. (2004) 'The Unified Medical Language System (UMLS): integrating biomedical terminology', *Nucleic Acids Research*, 32(Database issue), pp. D267–D270. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkh061>.
- CEDAR (2021) Metadata Center. Available at: <https://metadatacenter.org/> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- Google Dataset Search (no date). Available at: <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- F1: (Meta) data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (no date) GO FAIR. Available at: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/f1-meta-data-assigned-globally-unique-persistent-identifiers/> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- FAIR Digital Object Technical Overview (no date). Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/7824714> (Accessed: 16 May 2025).
- Hoebelheinrich, N.J. *et al.* (2025) 'A persona-specific method to assess the FAIRness of data repositories'. GO FAIR US. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13992886>.
- Interpreting FAIR (no date) GO FAIR Foundation. Available at: <https://www.gofair.foundation/interpretation> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- ISO 8601 — Date and time format (2017) ISO 8601. Available at: <https://www.iso.org/iso-8601-date-and-time-format.html> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- JSON for Linked Data (no date) JSON-LD. Available at: <https://json-ld.org/> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- Kuhn, T. *et al.* (2018) 'Nanopublications: A Growing Resource of Provenance-Centric Scientific Linked Data', in 2018 IEEE 14th International Conference on e-Science (e-Science). 2018 IEEE 14th International Conference on e-Science (e-Science), pp. 83–92. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1109/eScience.2018.00024>.
- Kuhn, T. (2019) 'peta-pico/cedar-nanopubs'. *peta pico web* (Cedar Nanopublications). Available at: <https://github.com/peta-pico/cedar-nanopubs> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- Lippincott, S. (2024) 'New at Dryad: Empowering reuse of cognitive neuroscience data', *Dryad news*, 9 April. Available at: <https://blog.datadryad.org/2024/04/09/new-at-dryad-empowering-reuse-of-cognitive-neuroscience-data/> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).
- Magagna, B. *et al.* (2025) 'Nanopublications as FAIR Digital Object Implementations', *Open Conference Proceedings*, 5. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.52825/ocp.v5i.1417>.

OBO Technical Working Group (no date) Open Biological and Biomedical Ontology Foundry, OBO Foundry. Available at: <https://obofoundry.org/>.

Olson, E. and Corker, K. (2024) 'Making It Easy to Make Specialized Research FAIR: Introducing Field-Specific Metadata Templates for OSF', Center for Open Science, 18 April. Available at: <https://www.cos.io/blog/cedar-embeddable-editor> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).

RDF Working Group (2014) RDF - Semantic Web Standards, W3C. Available at: <https://www.w3.org/RDF/> (Accessed: 15 May 2025).

Whetzel, P.L. *et al.* (2011) 'BioPortal: enhanced functionality via new Web services from the National Center for Biomedical Ontology to access and use ontologies in software applications', *Nucleic Acids Research*, 39(suppl_2), pp. W541–W545. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkr469>.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to the wider GO FAIR US team who are contributing to this project; Alyssa Arce, Kevin Coakley, Doug Fils, Barbara Magagna, Keith Maull, Matt Mayernik, Bert Meerman, Barend Mons and Erik Schultes. A special thanks also goes to Wilbert van Panhuis.

Funding information

This project has been funded in whole or in part with Federal funds from the National Cancer Institute, National Institutes of Health, under Contract No. 75N91019D00024, Task Order No. 75N91020F0022. The project is funded by the Frederick National Laboratory for Cancer Research, operated by Leidos Biomedical Research, Inc., on behalf of the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases. The content of this publication does not necessarily reflect the views or policies of the Department of Health and Human Services, nor does mention of trade names, commercial products, or organizations imply endorsement by the U.S. Government. Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s).

Author contributions

Nancy J. Hoebelheinrich: conceptualization, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing; John Graybeal: conceptualization, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing; Julianne Christopher: conceptualization, project administration, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing; Christopher Erdmann: writing – original draft; Ismael Kherroubi Garcia: writing – review & editing; Darya Pokutnaya – conceptualization; Lisa M. Mayer – conceptualization; Christine R. Kirkpatrick: conceptualization, project administration, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing